

Information on the application

Project title (maximum 25 words)*:

What makes code sharing scary? Moving towards an error culture where researchers feel comfortable to make their code available

(for a more engaging and productive code review processes)

Rationale* – Why is this project needed? What aspects of research culture and/or practice are addressed? (maximum 100 words):

Why do researchers applaud efforts to perform reproducibility checks and at the same time don't submit their work to said checks? How can we motivate people to share their code so that it is available for reuse? How can we make code and data checks less scary?

Participants will address perceived fears around code sharing in academia. The materials would ideally help not only with convincing researchers to share their work but also initialize a change in research culture where errors can be made, detected and revised without fear.

Planned output* – Describe the output that you would like to create, and estimate how complete this output will be at the end of the unconference (maximum 75 words):

- List of myths around code sharing (done by the end)
- List of perceived barriers and fears and how to reduce those (done by the end)
- Concrete communication materials (think: stickers, posters, catch-phrases; in a stage that it can be given to a design professional)
- (if there is interest) research proposal/ study plan to find out how researchers feel about code review and if that differs between domains

Target users* - Who would benefit from, or use, this output? (maximum 50 words)

Researchers and code stewards who want to normalize code sharing at their institutions, publishers and conference organizers who want to introduce reproducibility checks at their venues, providers of code registries who want to increase the use of their platforms

Desired participants for the project team* (maximum 50 words, bullet points encouraged)

- Specify which stakeholder groups are needed for this project (e.g., researchers, funders, publishers and editors, leadership of research institutions, others)
- List any specific expertise required for those who would join your project team during the unconference.

Researchers from a range of domains

Publishers, conference organizers

Code stewards, data stewards, professional reproducibility checkers

Desired¹ group size* - The maximum number of participants is 20 per group, however, leaders can request a smaller group if this better aligns with their project needs. ¹Please note, final group sizes for the unconference cannot be guaranteed due to the flexible event format.

No preference, there is enough room for 20 people

Space and logistical requirements – Please specify any special requirements needed to complete the proposed project (e.g., participants need to bring laptops and have internet access). (maximum 50 words, bullet points encouraged)

Laptops and internet access, if we are to work on communication materials: pens, large paper sheets

Planned schedule* – Please provide a short overview of activities that your group would work on during the unconference, outlining how you intend to engage participants in your project. Include specific strategies or activities you will use to foster interaction and collaboration. Project work will occur all day on September 23 and the morning of September 24, 2025, however, some time will be spent on meal breaks or synthesis sessions for all unconference attendees. (maximum 150 words, bullet points encouraged)

- September 23:
 - Introduction: problem statement, participants to share experiences, set-up (online) work environment, find common terminology (60 min)
 - Methods: Presentation, crossing-the line
 - Research phase: (120 min)
 - what is already out there
 - what myths are out there
 - what are arguments for/against

Methods: Activate social media followers, collect information online, collect arguments on flipcharts, use world café to narrow down arguments and extract the most relevant ones

○ Afternoon:

■ Work on materials – content level

Methods: Design Thinking – mapping users and arguments; for people to work on smaller/shorter projects: pick an argument or myth and see how you can turn it into a gimmick/poster/meme/sticker

● September 24

Recap (30 min)

Review and feedback on outputs (60 min)

Plan for continuation and dissemination of outputs (90 min)

Methods: open, depends on what comes out of the first day